

Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment Research Data Management Policy

JANUARI 2020

Preface

The Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment Research Data Management Policy is part of the central [TU Delft Research Data Framework Policy](#). This Policy helps create effective practices for working with research data at the faculty and defines data management roles and responsibilities of the different stakeholders within the faculty. This policy is supported by the [Definitions](#) and the [online guidance](#) on data management.

This Policy is motivated by the belief that good data stewardship leads to research that is more time- and cost-efficient and more research collaborations. To ensure the research is verifiable and allow people to elaborate based on the research (more transparent research process). It is inspired by principles that research data should be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR).

This policy cultivates:

- Good practice for ensuring that scientific arguments and results are transparent and, if applicable, reproducible in the long term.
- Better exposure of academic work of academic staff at TU Delft leading to recognition of quality of the research process as a whole.
- Responsible management of research data, including the safe storage of research data and protection of intellectual capital developed by scientists across TU Delft.
- Improved practices for meeting the demands of funders and publishers with respect to research data management and sharing.

This policy recognises that:

- Individual departments and research groups have different working practices and processes. Terms marked in orange in this document will be further supported by data stewards and related research services during the implementation.
- Data stewardship is the entire process of managing research data from its creation to its re-use and preservation and it is not equal to Open Science. While it is beneficial to publish research data openly, there might be valid ethical, legal, or commercial implications, which will make data unsuitable for open sharing.
- Research data (see [Definitions](#)) might mean different things for different disciplines. Source code, minutes, protocols, images and designs (drawings, models, mock-ups etc.) maps, prototypes, collections and other forms of information supporting publication/research output are also within the scope of this policy.

This faculty research data management policy is approved by the faculty management team and can be found [here](#)¹. The policy specified in this version is valid for 2020 - 2023.

Roles and Responsibilities

Note that the Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment Research Data Management Policy only specifies the Roles and Responsibilities of faculty-specific stakeholders. [TU Delft Research Data Framework Policy](#) should be consulted about the roles of the Library, ICT Department, University Services, and the Executive Board at TU Delft.

Individual academic staff are expected to:

- Ensure that research data, code and any other materials needed to reproduce or justify research findings are appropriately documented, stored and shared in a research data repository in accordance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) for at least 10 years from the end of the research project, unless there are valid reasons not to do so.
- Should data not be made available in a repository, ensure that the data management plan and any research publications resulting from the project have a statement explaining what additional datasets/materials exists; why access is restricted; who can use the data and under what circumstances.
- Understand who owns research data resulting from their projects and what that implies in terms of data management, particularly regarding sharing and publishing.
- Undertake training in good data management if needed or suggested by supervisors or departmental research directors.

In addition, PhD students are expected to:

- Develop a written data management strategy for managing research outputs within the first 12 months of the PhD study. (Obligatory for all PhDs starting on/ from 1 January 2020.)
- Attend the relevant training in data management.
- Ensure that all data and code underlying completed PhD theses are appropriately documented and accessible for at least 10 years from the end of the research project, in accordance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable), unless there are valid reasons which make research data unsuitable for sharing. (Obligatory for all PhDs starting on/from 1 January 2019.)

PhD Supervisors are responsible for:

- Supporting their PhD students in preparation of a written data management plan for managing research outputs within the first 12 months of the PhD study. (Obligatory for all PhDs starting on/from 1 January 2020.)
 - Discussing data management plan in the go-no-go review at the end of the first year PhD study. The go-no-go decision is independent from the data management plan.
- Ensuring that PhD students attend relevant training on data management.
- Ensuring that their PhD students make all data and code underlying their

completed PhD theses appropriately documented and accessible for at least 10 years from the end of the research project, in accordance with the FAIR principles, unless there are valid reasons which make research data unsuitable for sharing. (Obligatory for all PhDs starting on/from 1 January 2019.)

Principal investigators / Departmental research coordinator are responsible for:

- Ensuring that all members of the departments / sections / chairs (including PhDs) are aware of the FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) and are appropriately trained to effectively manage research data, and that they adhere to the expectations outlined within this policy.
 - Ensure that all members of the group plan for good data management from the outset of any research project and adhere to good data management practice throughout the project's lifecycle.
- Ensuring that any agreements with external funding agencies, commercial companies or other third parties allow compliance with this Data Policy
 - Adhere to **contractual obligations** with regards to **ownership** of, and rights relating to, research datasets resulting from projects funded by external agencies or commercial companies.
- Budgeting for data management **costs** into financial project planning at the proposal stage.
- Working with the faculty data steward to develop practical data management solutions within the department / sections / chairs.

Department chairman are responsible for:

- Ensuring awareness of good data management practices among all academic staff within the department.
- Developing effective strategies for monitoring and review of data management practices.
- Encouraging to adopt good data management practices among all academic staff.
- Encouraging to discuss practices and experience of data management during the annual R&O meeting with individual academic staff.

Data Stewards are responsible for:

- Leading the development, review and implementation of the faculty's data management policy and reference guide.
- Creating awareness and explain to academic staff the added value of good data management.
- Assisting academic staff in planning the collection, management, and publication of data in research projects and liaise with other service providers (such as Legal services, ICT, Human Research Ethics Committee) as required.
- Helping academic staff with writing data management plans and with budgeting for research data management costs in their grant applications.
- Searching, informing, or organizing training events tailored to academic staff needs. Helping to incorporate good data management practices into existing curriculum.

Faculty Dean is responsible for:

- Ensuring that Data Stewards are embedded within the faculty.
- Faculty Policies for Research Data Management based on this framework
- Ensuring that within their faculty there is appropriate infrastructure and the right tools for academic staff to put good data management into practice.
- Ensuring that necessary **training and advocacy** provisions are available to the faculty, and that academic staff are aware of the faculty's data management policy and are equipped with adequate skills to adhere to it.

Colofon

From the BK website:

<https://www.tudelft.nl/en/architecture-and-the-built-environment/about-the-faculty/about-the-faculty/>

The faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment has a leading role in education and research worldwide. The driving force behind the faculty's success is its robust research profile combined with the passion and creativity of its student body and academic community. It is a place that is buzzing with life from early in the morning until late at night, with four thousand people studying, working, designing, conducting research and acquiring and disseminating knowledge. Academics and students have been working on improving the built environment with the help of a broad set of disciplines, including architectural design, urban planning, building technology, social sciences, process management, and geo-information science. The faculty works closely with other faculties, universities, private parties, and the public sector, and has an extensive network in the Netherlands as well as internationally.

Contact info:

<https://www.tudelft.nl/en/architecture-and-the-built-environment/about-the-faculty/contact-and-map/>

T: +31 (0)15 27 89 805

Building 8

Julianalaan 134

2628 BL Delft

Data Steward:

Yan Wang

E: Y.Wang-16@tudelft.nl

Design:

Nina Noordzij | [Collage](#), Grou

Photograph:

Communication BK